

Electronic Cash Based on *Batch* Groth- Sahai

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Abstract. Electronic cash is a form of electronic currency that enables cash transactions over communication networks while ensuring privacy. Electronic money necessitates the verification of a user's identity to ascertain whether a user of electronic money is legitimate. There are various identity verification methods, one of which is the Groth-Sahai proof. In this study, the Groth-Sahai proof is enhanced to include batch processing steps for identity verification. The results of the batch Groth-Sahai method were utilized in the verification process for electronic money.

Introduction

In 1983, David Chaum[1] proposed a cryptographic scheme aimed at enabling untraceable digital payments, laying the groundwork for the development of electronic cash. Following Chaum's pioneering work, many scholars worldwide have sought to enhance and implement various types of electronic money systems. For example, in 1988, Lysyanskaya and Ramzan[2] made a significant contribution by creating the first multi-bank electronic payment system that had both blind and group signatures. However, according to Zhou et al.(2016)[3], electronic cash systems continue to face significant challenges. In particular, they still struggle to meet the following three important conditions:

1. The system is built on a random oracle, where a random oracle is a process of finding the output from the input given with an unknown process.
2. The system does not support large numbers of banks and dynamic user integration.
3. The cost of making a system is expensive because, for one electronic money-making, the system requires three iterations at each stage.

Problems numbers 1 and 3 can be solved by implementing Non-Interactive Zero Knowledge Proof (NIZK), which Groth and Sahai popularized in 2012[4]. While resolving problem number 2 can be solved by implementing dynamic group signatures that were popularized by Bellare et al. in 2005 [5]. The concept of dynamic group signature is based on the idea of group signatures that Chaum came up with in 1991[6]. With group signatures, any member of the group can

sign messages on behalf of the group without revealing their identity. A unique and fixed group public key can be used to check the authenticity of the signature.

In 2010, Blazy et al [7]. used batch verification to accelerate the running time of the NIZK that Groth and Sahai[4] popularized. Due to the addition of the batch verification, Blazy et al. named the NIZK, which was obtained as the Batch Groth-Sahai. In this study, an electronic cash system was examined using Batch Groth-Sahai.

Electronic cash

According to Zhou et al. (2016)[3], there are three important elements in the electronic cash system, namely the central bank, local banks, and users, where the users consist of traders and buyers. The task of the central bank includes providing certificates to local banks and storing information on local banks and users at the time of registration to manage and revoke their rights from the system if necessary. Local banks can make electronic cash and sign it anonymously. After that, customers can send electronic cash to merchants offering goods and services, and traders can deposit electronic cash into the bank only if the electronic cash is legal. If there is a dispute between the parties concerned, then one of them can apply to the central bank to obtain the identity of the other party and execute the arbitration. The steps of the electronic cash system based on batch Groth-Sahai are defined as follows:

1. *Setup* (1^k) \rightarrow (p, G, G_T, e, g)

In the setup, the input used is (1^k) where (k) is the security parameter. The output of this step is the public key of the central bank (PK), the extract key (tk), the public group key of the local bank (pk), and the private key of the local bank signature (d), which (d) is used to issue electronic money and signatures.

1 Bilinear Setup

The central bank uses $\text{BilinearSetup}(1^k)$ to generate the parameters (p, G, G_T, e, g), where $e : G \times G \rightarrow G_T$ and G and G_T have the same order p . Take $(x, y, r, ru, sv) \in Z_p^5$ and $z \in Z_p^*$, then calculate $f = g^x$, $h = g^y$, $\Omega = g^r$, and $(u, v, w) = (f^{ru}, h^{sv}, g^{ru+sv+z})$. Then it (u, v, w) is shared with the public. Create a hash function $H : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^n$. Take the vector $(\vec{u}, \vec{v}, \vec{w}) \in G^3$, where each vector is $\vec{u} = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$, $\vec{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$, and $\vec{w} = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$.

2 The Next Step

The central bank chooses $a \in Z_n$ as the secret key, then calculates $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2) = (g^a, g^{a^2})$ as the public key, and $tk = (x, y, z)$ as the opening key to open an identity if needed.

The local bank chooses $(r', k) \in Z_q^{*2}$, where k is the secret key of the

local bank, then calculates $d = \{d_1, d_2\} = \{g^{ar'}, g^{ak}g^{r'}\}$ the secret key of the local bank, and the local bank calculates $pk = g^k$ the public key.

2. *Register* ($M_i : PK, sk_i, pk_i; Centralbank : pk$) \rightarrow ($M_i : C_{ID}; Centralbank : Reg[ID]$)

This stage consists of two parts: the local bank registration section and user registration for those who want to join. The input is in the form of a secret key (SK) and a public key from each party wishing to register. The central bank will then create a certificate for the party while simultaneously entering the user and local bank certificates into the registration list. The registration procedures are similar, so only the registration for local banks is discussed.

- 1 *Bank i* : $(k, g^k) \leftrightarrow$ *Central bank* : (g^k) *Bank i* chooses $k \in Z_q^*$ then calculates the public key $pk = g^k$ and gives it to the central bank.
- 2 *Central bank* \rightarrow *Bank i* : $(cert_{B_i})$ The central bank uses the local bank's public key g^k and a random number $id \in Z_n$ to create a certificate $cert_{B_i} = (sigma_1, sigma_2) = ((h.pk)^{\frac{1}{r+id}}, g^{id})$, then calculates $c_{ID} = H(sigma_1, sigma_2)$ and stores it inside $reg[ID]$.
- 3 *Bank i* \rightarrow *Central bank* : $(cert_{B_i})$ *Bank i* will ensure the equation $e(sigma_1, Omega sigma_2) = e(g, h)e(g, pk)$ is right. If it's incorrect, the bank will send the value $c = H(sigma_1, sigma_2)$ to the central bank. Then the central bank will equate this value with c_{ID} .

3. *Open* (C_{ID}, pk, d) \rightarrow (Σ)

At this stage, the user utilizes his (C_{id}) certificate to create and send a statement (Σ) to the local bank, which will confirm the user's certificate.

- 1 *User* \rightarrow *Bank i* : (Σ)

User creates a certificate C , where C defined as

$$C = (C_1, C_2, C_3) = \left(f^r \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{c_i}, h^s \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{c_i}, g^{r+S} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{c_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

With $(r, s, t) \in Z_p^3$ where c_i is the i -th bit on C_{ID} . After that, the user makes NIZK (π_1, π_2, π_3) with C ,

$$\pi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\pi}_{1,1} \\ \vec{\pi}_{1,2} \\ \vec{\pi}_{1,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (f^r \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{2c_i-1})^r \\ h^{rs-t} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{(2c_i-1)r} \\ g^{(r+s)r+t} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)r} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\pi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\pi}_{2,1} \\ \vec{\pi}_{2,2} \\ \vec{\pi}_{2,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f^{rs+t} \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{(2c_i-1)s} \\ (h^r \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{2c_i-1})^s \\ g^{(r+s)r-t} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)s} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\pi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\pi}_{3,1} \\ \vec{\pi}_{3,2} \\ \vec{\pi}_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\pi}_{1,1} \cdot \vec{\pi}_{2,1} \\ \vec{\pi}_{1,2} \cdot \vec{\pi}_{2,2} \\ \vec{\pi}_{1,3} \cdot \vec{\pi}_{2,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f^{r(r+s)+t} \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \\ h^{s(r+s)-t} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \\ g^{2r(r+s)} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Then the user sends a statement Σ to the bank. Where Σ is $\{\pi_1, \pi_2, \pi_3, C\}$.

2 *Bank i* \rightarrow *User* : (valid/invalid)

The bank verifies the statement Σ sent by the user in the following way:

$$e(f, \pi_{1,1}\pi_{1,2}\pi_{1,3}\pi_{2,2}\pi_{2,3}\pi_{3,3}) \cdot e(h, \pi_{2,1}\pi_{3,1}\pi_{3,2}) = e\left(C_1, C_1C_2C_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{-1}\right)^2\right) \cdot e\left(C_2C_3, C_1C_2C_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1}\right)^3\right) \quad (5)$$

4. Withdraw

At this step, the local bank creates a C_{iD} certificate as in the registration stage and generates a statement Σ . Then, the local bank uses the central bank's public key along with its own secret key to create a signature for electronic money M and σ issues it to the user. The user verifies the local bank's statement Σ and checks the local.

1. *Bank i* \rightarrow *User* : (Γ)

Bank *i* verifies and proves the statement Σ from the user. Then bank *i* will make a statement Σ_{bank} using C_{iD} obtained from the registration stage, where

$$\Sigma_{bank} = \{\phi = [\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3], E = [E_1, E_2, E_3]\},$$

where E is a certificate similar to an equation in the open stage, which is built from the C_{iD} bank *i* and ϕ is the NIZK to verify the banks identity. Bank *i* chooses $t' \in Z_q^*$, to calculate the signature string $\delta = \{U_1, U_2, V_1, V_2\} = \{g^{a^2t'}, g^{ar't'}, d_1^h, d_2^{r+h}\}$ where $h = H(m, U_1, U_2)$. Then the signature $ttd = H(U_1, U_2, V_1, V_2)$ is formed, where $ttd \in \{0, 1\}^n$ and the certificate

$$D = (D_1, D_2, D_3) = (f^r \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{ttd_i}, h^s \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{ttd_i}, g^{r+s} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{ttd_i}) \quad (6)$$

with $(r, s, t) \in Z_p^3$ and ttd_i is the i -th bit on ttd . then NIZK $\varphi = (\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3)$ is made with certificate D ,

$$\varphi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi}_{1,1} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{1,2} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{1,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (f^r \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{2c_i-1})^r \\ h^{rs-t} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{(2c_i-1)r} \\ g^{(r+s)r+t} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)r} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi}_{2,1} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{2,2} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{2,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f^{rs+t} \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{(2c_i-1)s} \\ (h^r \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{2c_i-1})^s \\ g^{(r+s)r-t} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)s} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi}_{3,1} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{3,2} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{\varphi}_{11} \cdot \vec{\varphi}_{2,1} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{12} \cdot \vec{\varphi}_{2,2} \\ \vec{\varphi}_{1,3} \cdot \vec{\varphi}_{2,3} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f^{r(r+s)+t} \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \\ h^{s(r+s)-t} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \\ g^{2r(r+s)} \prod_{i=1}^n w_i^{(2c_i-1)(r+s)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Then bank i send a statement (Γ, \sum_{bank}) to the user. where Γ is

$$\Gamma = \{\delta, (\varphi, D)\}. \quad (10)$$

2. User : accept/reject

First, the user proves the statement \sum_{bank} from the bank, and then the user checks the statement (φ, D) in Equation 10 that is correct by completing Equation 11. If everything has been done and proven correct, the signature in Equation 10 can be used.

$$e(f, \varphi_{11}\varphi_{12}\varphi_{13}\varphi_{22}\varphi_{23}\varphi_{33}) e(h, \varphi_{21}\varphi_{31}\varphi_{32}) = e\left(D_1, D_1 D_2 D_3 \prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \left(\prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{-1}\right)^2\right) e\left(D_2 D_3, D_1 D_2 D_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1}\right)^3\right) \quad (11)$$

5. Spend

1. $User_C \rightarrow User_M : (M)$

Suppose a transaction occurs, which we will call R . To avoid two payments, the buyer calculates $S = F_s(i)$, and the value of non-double spending $T = g^{CID} F_r(i)^R$ then sends $M = \{S, T, \Gamma, \sum_{bank}, \sum\}$ as electronic money to traders.

2. $User_M : (accept/reject)$

$$\begin{aligned}
& e \left(\left(f, \begin{array}{c} \varphi_{11}\varphi_{12}\varphi_{13}\varphi_{22}\varphi_{23}\varphi_{33}\pi_{11}\pi_{12}\pi_{13}\pi_{22}\pi_{23}\pi_{33} \\ \phi_{11}\phi_{12}\phi_{13}\phi_{22}\phi_{23}\phi_{33} \end{array} \right) e \left(h, \varphi_{21}\varphi_{31}\varphi_{32}\pi_{21}\pi_{31}\pi_{32}\phi_{21}\phi_{31}\phi_{32} \right) = \\
& e \left(C_1, C_1 C_2 C_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{-1} \right)^2 \right) e \left(C_2 C_3, C_1 C_2 C_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \right)^3 \right) \\
& e \left(E_1, E_1 E_2 E_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{-1} \right)^2 \right) e \left(E_2 E_3, E_1 E_2 E_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \right)^3 \right) \\
& e \left(D_1, D_1 D_2 D_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \prod_{i=1}^n v_i^{-1} \right)^2 \right) e \left(D_2 D_3, D_1 D_2 D_3 \left(\prod_{i=1}^n u_i^{-1} \right)^3 \right) \\
& \hspace{15em} (12)
\end{aligned}$$

6. Deposit

1. $User_m \rightarrow Bank\ i$

The trader gives the obtained statement (Σ, Γ) to the bank.

2. $Bank\ i \rightarrow User_m : (C)$

Bank i verifies the trader's identity with two stages. First verifying the trader's statement Σ correctly, then verifying (φ, D) the statement Γ sent by the merchant correctly.

7. Trace

1. $Bank\ i \rightarrow Bank\ central : (C)$

If a problem occurs, bank i sends the user's C value to the central bank, and then the central bank uses the extraction key tk to get the C_{ID} of the signatory's by,

$$(g^z)^{C_{ID}} = C_3 C_1^{-\frac{1}{x}} C_2^{-\frac{1}{y}} \quad (13)$$

Then check $C_{ID} \text{ reg}[ID]$ which satisfies Equation 13.

Conditions for correctness, anonymity, unforgettability, traceability, and non-double spending are needed to ensure the security of the electronic cash system.

Performance analysis

Based on the explanation of the method of research on electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai, the fact is that both electronic cash systems have a dynamic nature of joining, and there is not much interaction needed to prove the signature issued from the bank i to the user. If we compare it with [3] then conclusions are found as in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of Characteristics of Electronic Money Based on Groth-Sahai with Electronic Money Based on Batch Groth-Sahai.

Electronic Cash	Non-interactive	Dynamically to join
Electronic Cash based on Groth-Sahai Proof	Y	Y
Electronic Cash based on Batch Groth-Sahai	Y	Y

The security of electronic cash, seen from the explanation in the research method regarding electronic cash security based on batch Groth-Sahai, these systems are in common with fulfilling the conditions proposed by Zhou et al.[3], namely correctness, anonymity, unforgeability, traceability, and non-double spending. According to Zhou et al.[3], When electronic cash is made by fulfilling the anonymity requirements proposed by it, the resulting electronic cash can survive a chosen cipher attack (CCA), where CCA is defined as an attack model where hackers can extract information by decrypting a ciphertext. If we compare it with [3] then conclusions are found as in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Security of Electronic Money Based on Groth-Sahai with Electronic Money Based on Batch Groth-Sahai.

Electronic Cash	Correctness	Anonymity	Unforgeability	Traceability	Non-Double Spending
Electronic Cash based on Groth-Sahai Proof	Y	CCA	Y	Y	Y
Electronic Cash based on Batch Groth-Sahai	Y	CCA	Y	Y	Y

The difference in electronic money can be seen in the number of pairings completed to verify one signature, with electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai completing fewer pairs. For example, at the spending stage, electronic cash based on Groth-Sahai batch completes eight pairs, while electronic cash based on Groth-Sahai Proof completed a number of 54 pairs. Therefore, electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai was faster at verifying the validity of the user's signature, for the number of interactions to verify a signature has the same amount, namely 1. If we compare it with [3], then conclusions are found as in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Security Cost of Electronic Money Based on Groth-Sahai with Electronic Money Based on Batch Groth-Sahai.

Electronic Cash	Open	Withdraw	Spend	Deposit	Interaction
Electronic Cash based on Groth-Sahai Proof	18	36	54	36	1
Electronic Cash based on Batch Groth-Sahai	4	16	8	16	1

Conclusion

Electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai fulfills the security requirements proposed by Zhou et al.[3], where the security requirements are correctness,

unforgettability, anonymity, traceability, and non-double spending. Electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai also has the nature of users being able to join dynamically and does not require much interaction to verify a signature because of the number of interactions needed to verify the signature is one. In the process of verifying one signature, electronic cash based on batch Groth-Sahai completes a smaller number of pairings, for example at the spending stage, the electronic cash batch Groth-Sahai proves as many as eight pairs. This is less than the number of pairings that must be completed to verify one signature on electronic cash stated by Zhou et al.[3], which is equal to 54 pairings.

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